

A. Instance Selection Protocol

Seed instances were selected from the CIFAR-10 test split using the target classifier adopted in the experiments. We first evaluated the classifier on the full test split and retained only correctly classified examples. This ensures that each local search starts from a correctly classified seed image whose predicted label matches the ground-truth label. Consequently, a discovered class change corresponds to a local decision-boundary crossing rather than to the exploitation of an initially misclassified input.

To avoid class-specific bias, instance selection was performed independently within each CIFAR-10 class. For each class, correctly classified examples were sorted according to the classifier confidence assigned to the predicted class. The sorted examples were then divided into three equal-sized strata, corresponding to low-, medium-, and high-confidence regimes. These regimes are defined relative to each class, rather than by global confidence thresholds, so that the protocol preserves class-specific confidence distributions while still covering different levels of expected local boundary accessibility.

For the representative evaluation subset, we selected one instance from each class-confidence stratum, yielding $10 \times 3 = 30$ seed instances. Although compact, this subset is designed for controlled local analysis rather than for estimating global classifier accuracy. Each seed defines a local decision-boundary crossing task, and all methods are evaluated on the same tasks under matched budgets and repeated runs. This yields a balanced benchmark over semantic classes and confidence regimes while keeping the computational cost feasible for population-based and iterative black-box optimizers. The goal is therefore not to exhaustively sample CIFAR-10, but to compare how different search heuristics behave when exposed to the same diverse set of local boundary conditions.

The representative instance was chosen as the example whose confidence was closest to the median confidence of its stratum. Ties were broken by selecting the instance with the larger top-1/top-2 probability margin and then, if necessary, the smaller dataset index. This median-based criterion avoids selecting extreme or manually chosen examples while preserving coverage across semantic classes and confidence regimes. Figure 1 provides a visual check of this protocol: the selected representatives cover all classes and confidence regimes while remaining within their corresponding per-class confidence distributions.

All optimization methods were evaluated on the same selected seed instances. This controls for variation in the starting points and ensures that observed differences reflect the behavior of the search heuristics under the same local decision-boundary crossing tasks. The full selection procedure is deterministic given the classifier outputs and dataset indices, and the resulting seeds are reported together with their class labels, confidence values, and confidence strata to support reproducibility.

Fig. 1. Representative seed selection over the per-class confidence distributions. Box-plots show the classifier confidence distribution of correctly classified CIFAR-10 test examples for each class, while markers indicate the selected representatives from the low-, medium-, and high-confidence strata. The selected instances remain within their corresponding class distributions, supporting the use of the reduced seed set as a compact and balanced evaluation subset.

B. Flip Success Rate (Sanity Check)

As an initial sanity check, Fig. 2 shows that the task is not trivial for unguided exploration, but it is also not difficult enough to clearly separate the guided optimizers in terms of final success. GA, CMA-ES, and hill climbing all achieved a flip success rate of 1.00, whereas random search succeeded in only 30% of the runs. This result indicates that, under the adopted search budget, a guided strategy is already sufficient to reliably cross the local decision boundary, while pure random exploration often fails.

For this reason, Fig. 2 should be interpreted mainly as a validation of the setup rather than as a substantive comparison among the main search methods. The more informative differences emerge when we examine efficiency, confidence regime, and locality of the solutions.

C. Additional Statistical Results

This appendix reports consolidated numerical summaries and supplementary statistical tests supporting the visual analyses presented in the main text. Table 1 provides descriptive summaries for success, time to first flip, and best-flip distance across methods. Table 2 reports the main global tests used to support the comparisons in the results section. Tables 3–6 provide post-hoc pairwise comparisons for the main outcomes. For best-flip distance and unique-valid-flip analyses, comparisons were performed over matched evaluation blocks, where each block corresponds to the same underlying source instance and confidence stratum evaluated across methods; random search was excluded from these paired

Fig. 2. Flip success rate by algorithm. GA, CMA-ES, and hill climbing achieve success in all runs, whereas random search succeeds in only 30% of them, making this result primarily a sanity check that guided search is necessary and effective in the local boundary-crossing task.

Table 1. Consolidated summary of success, time to first flip, and best-flip distance across methods. Confidence intervals are reported at the 95% level. For random search, best-flip distance is computed only over successful runs and should therefore be interpreted jointly with its substantially lower success rate.

Method	Runs	Successes	Success rate	95% CI	Median time	IQR time	95% CI time	Median best-flip distance	IQR	95% CI
CMA-ES	150	150	1.00	[0.975, 1.000]	474.0	627.75	[362.0, 614.0]	0.2173	0.0190	[0.2144, 0.2196]
GA	150	150	1.00	[0.975, 1.000]	126.5	127.5	[117.0, 151.5]	0.3335	0.1252	[0.3136, 0.3490]
Hill	150	150	1.00	[0.975, 1.000]	125.5	118.0	[107.5, 202.0]	0.2956	0.0819	[0.2924, 0.3627]
Random	150	45	0.30	[0.2324, 0.3776]	20100.0	11417.25	[20100.0, 20100.0]	0.1992	0.0030	[0.1982, 0.2004]

block-level tests because its substantially lower success rate makes its best-flip distances conditional on a non-comparable subset of successful runs.

Table 2. Main global statistical tests supporting the results section.

Test	Scope	Statistic	p
Log-rank	Overall time to first flip	$\chi^2 = 487.50$	2.44×10^{-105}
Friedman	Overall best-flip distance	$\chi^2 = 29.58$	1.69×10^{-6}

Table 3. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons for time to first flip among guided methods. Adjusted p-values were computed with the Holm correction.

Comparison	n	Statistic	p	p_{Holm}
CMA-ES vs GA	300	121.61	2.80×10^{-28}	5.61×10^{-28}
CMA-ES vs Hill	300	145.20	1.94×10^{-33}	5.83×10^{-33}
GA vs Hill	300	1.73	1.89×10^{-1}	1.89×10^{-1}

Table 4. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons for time to first flip stratified by confidence group. Adjusted p-values were computed with the Holm correction within each stratum.

Confidence group	Comparison	n	Statistic	p	p_{Holm}
Low	CMA-ES vs GA	100	49.75	1.74×10^{-12}	3.49×10^{-12}
Low	CMA-ES vs Hill	100	52.16	5.11×10^{-13}	1.53×10^{-12}
Low	GA vs Hill	100	1.84	1.75×10^{-1}	1.75×10^{-1}
Medium	CMA-ES vs GA	100	37.69	8.31×10^{-10}	1.66×10^{-9}
Medium	CMA-ES vs Hill	100	41.80	1.01×10^{-10}	3.03×10^{-10}
Medium	GA vs Hill	100	4.42	3.55×10^{-2}	3.55×10^{-2}
High	CMA-ES vs GA	100	54.17	1.84×10^{-13}	3.68×10^{-13}
High	CMA-ES vs Hill	100	72.13	2.02×10^{-17}	6.06×10^{-17}
High	GA vs Hill	100	0.14	7.05×10^{-1}	7.05×10^{-1}

Table 5. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons for best-flip distance. Adjusted p-values were computed with the Holm correction. Negative median differences indicate that the first method achieved smaller best-flip distances than the second.

Comparison	Blocks	Statistic	p	p_{Holm}	Rank-biserial	Median diff. (A-B)
CMA-ES vs GA	30	3.0	9.31×10^{-9}	2.79×10^{-8}	-0.9871	-0.1116
CMA-ES vs Hill	30	3.0	9.31×10^{-9}	2.79×10^{-8}	-0.9871	-0.1062
GA vs Hill	30	184.0	3.28×10^{-1}	3.28×10^{-1}	-0.2086	-0.0012

Table 6. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons for the number of unique valid flips. Adjusted p-values were computed with the Holm correction. Positive median differences indicate that the first method recovered more unique flips than the second.

Comparison	Blocks	Statistic	p	p_{Holm}	Rank-biserial	Median diff. (A-B)
CMA-ES vs GA	30	187.5	3.55×10^{-1}	3.55×10^{-1}	0.1935	1099.5
CMA-ES vs Hill	30	65.5	5.93×10^{-4}	1.78×10^{-3}	-0.7183	-1472.5
GA vs Hill	30	109.0	9.93×10^{-3}	1.99×10^{-2}	-0.5312	-2187.0